

LGBT et al.

This is an essay about identity, creativity, and probably human rights.

Our identities are as real and vulnerable as any part of our body and just as stoutly defended. They start from scratch, grow by being nurtured and then develop with our help as we get older. The challenge that this essay proposes is that anyone with an identity 'like this' could equally well have turned out 'like that'. There is resistance to this aspect of reality for a variety of reasons, not least because it is the essence of an adult identity *not* to be anyone else. Most of those who are sceptical are usually prepared to compromise and are tolerant towards difference, but still politely deny the possibility of being 'like that'. As I hope to show, there is much more at stake than tolerance, essential though it is.

An identity is not floating in virtual space, it is part of the human brain, so I will need to make a number of general points about the way the brain works, and in particular the mind. We think and we communicate with others using language, and this brain activity is the 'mind'; the mind is the activity of the brain when it is handling language. From the 'inside', the mind *is* that language activity with all its attached feelings. This sentence is a particular form of the operation of my mind, and while I was concentrating on constructing it, I (my mind) was doing that and nothing else. You can see that the words 'I', my 'identity' and 'my language' indicate part of the same thing, some 'thing' that exists, but not in any static form. My identity is the outcome of my life history, and any attempt by me to seize the quintessence of that identity could only consist of an active mental reconstruction in language of what would still represent only one facet of my identity. I am making these picky points early on to emphasise what the word 'mind' means and because the idea of a 'constructed' identity is important for what follows.

I will open the discussion by considering the question of the male gender. Gender refers to a particular relationship of the mind with the body, a relationship that demonstrates very clearly why an individual has sovereign rights over their identity. I will explain that, and why, the identity 'man' is not predetermined by the genes; there is no reason to assume that a 'male' mind, the social construction, must be tied to a male body, even though that is what usually happens. First though, I will explain how the male gender is understood generally, but incorrectly. Then I will describe how the male gender is constructed, and this explanation of gender identity construction will lead me back to the title of the essay.

Before I go any further, I want to proclaim the innocence of a steroid hormone falsely accused of many crimes: testosterone...

Despite its well-known effects on the body, this steroid hormone is not responsible for male behaviour, however idiotic; but since it is central to most people's understanding of the male gender, I need to be more explicit. The following illustration should help if I can explain it clearly.

The fate of the boy on the left illustrates the way the development of masculinity is seen almost universally. He grows normally and at puberty his testosterone starts to act on his body and on him. Male hormone-driven behaviour patterns appear that the boy learns to manage more or less well: aggression, domination, various aspects of virility... Finally, the man is all one would have hoped for: his gender identity is definitely male (odd question!), and his testosterone keeps him that way. This description might be adapted to account for different degrees of maleness (again incorrectly), but it does not deal with becoming gay. (Warning: the 'science' in this area is a disaster.)

The first thing to note with the second boy's route to manhood is that there is no testosterone involved in the process, even if the body is chock-full of it. The graphic also illustrates, hopefully, that the route to the mind of the adult man is a process of identity construction. I do not want to raise the issue of thinkish here, even though the

thinking behind thinkish is the logical basis of this account; what I did want to indicate in the graphic is the building block-type construction of the identity as the youngster is growing up. These 'blocks' are bits and pieces of language that the youngster hears, very often simply the language habits of the adults who raise him. His active brain organises what it absorbs so as to keep its owner happy and this means that the values implicit in what is heard may be modified in the mind of the youngster in the process of asserting an independent identity. (If the brain should fail or be prevented from doing that, its owner will be 'mentally ill'.) In general – and this is one of the consequences of us all being born good sorts - if the boy is raised in the culture of the real man (say), that's most likely how he will end up, because he will be happiest being that way. The environments in which children are raised are hardly likely to be simple mono-cultures though. I will stick my neck out and say that one of the most potent influences on the young brain will surely be the 'gender politics' going on around it, because the politicking will be between potential role models that the baby brain is keen to copy. It will be tough on this lad if his brain picks up signals that for one reason or another do not fit, disrupting the expected outcome. I don't need to elaborate on the greater freedom that a more liberal (and, for difference, less painful) upbringing will allow. The point that I am making is that the gender identity of this youngster is not 'natured' by his hormones and his body, but created and nurtured by interaction with his culture.

The early days are the trickiest to discuss but they are obviously key, so it is worth making some observations about the trusty brain. The brain's golden rule is 'keep my owner safe and happy with whatever works'. To assess the real world, to build its model of the world if you like, the brain finds 'whatever works' by copying and best-guessing. Think of the brain as an artisan learning from practical experience and passed-down practices because it is certainly neither a scientist nor a moralist; those possibilities only arrive when a more sophisticated mind develops. It is the early brain activity that forms the roots of the gender, before the sex hormones appear, and before the mind has reached the stage of finger-wagging about what the gender 'ought' to be.

Looking from the point of view of human biology at what I have outlined - social identity construction - the evolution of mind (language, same thing) can be seen as a takeover of the individual 'animal'. The overwhelming importance of a social identity in our biology has resulted in even such a binary function as sex, as it is when it serves the purpose of reproduction, becoming transformed by our language into gender, thereby creating an element in the construction of a social identity. From this enlightened point of view, we can say that it just happens that human culture is set up – for pretty obvious biological and historical reasons – to produce two genders. By thinking in terms of a construction path to a gender identity, the outcome is seen to be the result of the culture that a youngster grows up in, not of the inexorable action of genes and hormones, as it is for his body. The cultural information adopted by the brain will signpost the path to the final gender identity label. Our genders are constructed according to the universal biological principle: whatever works; and the sure sign of what is working for mental life is well-being. The thinkish route (to call it that) may operate relatively freely, but it

can also be controlled tightly and so is equally capable of forging the iron man as nurturing the new man. In one culture, the new man may be the paradigm, in another the iron man. Don't forget what real men say: they'll be back.

Even if my graphic hardly credits what I imagine are the complexities and subtleties of gender construction, it does make it possible to understand that because of this mechanism, the gender identity is in principle a fuzzy concept. Instead of two genders, I can speak of 'the-brain-pleases-itself-if-it's-possible' genders; if it's not possible, you will end up feeling locked in the closet. Is there any evidence for this state of affairs? Obviously there is, and no cocktail of steroid hormones will ever explain it. So what I have indicated in the following graphic is the idea that *nurture* is sufficiently rich in possibilities that it can produce a rainbow of identities... LGBT et al.

To be more precise, a liberal culture permits a spectrum of gender identity labels with which the owners can be at ease; our western culture is pretty much at that point or on the way, a result of a mixture of tolerance and insistence.

I recognise that this description of gender identity will come up against a brick wall of very fixed ideas: *this is a perfect example of the need to impose decency and order, by force if necessary. Without going so far as to invoke divine law, why can't you see that, for reasons of genetics, LGBT brains are brains that didn't quite make it into one of the two natural channels? Maybe we shouldn't go so far as to administer steroid hormones to correct the fault, but still...* The drawback of a society that is ignorantly tolerant is that it can all too easily become ignorantly intolerant and therefore feel that it is never guilty of repression. The soft power of tolerance is not always around to resist the forces of ignorance or dogma.

One particularly poisonous element in the misunderstanding of identity is the belief

in the power of genetic 'traits': saints and sinners, sheep and wolves and of course, geniuses, are born, not made. It is important to stress the consequences of the logic of this way of understanding the identity. Believing that genetic traits dominate nurture by worming their way irremediably into the identity of the 'other' provides a false sense of security in one's own identity in situations such as: this new-born, with these genetic traits, will be gay; or again: this baby will grow up to be someone who could send thousands of people to the gas chamber. The problems caused by hiding behind genetic traits and denying the principle of 'like that' are manifold but perhaps the most serious is the denial of the potential contribution of each of us to the 'banality of evil'; and it's only a short hop from genetic traits to race, remember.

On the other hand, it would be silly to deny that physical traits influence the development of an individual's capabilities. If you are not strong enough, you can't lift a heavy weight, if you are not intelligent enough, you will never be a theoretical physicist and if you have the bits and pieces of a boy, you will never physically be a girl. Fortunately our brains have a sense of humour when it comes to physical traits and can keep them in their place: their place is secondary to the social status and well-being of the individual. (I should inform you at this point that I'm perfectly intelligent, just in my own way.) Ideally, physical capacities are evaluated by the brain and mind in such a way that there is no risk to the status of the individual, but whether physical (or acquired) traits end up being managed well or badly in the real world is another matter. Look once again at the social environment that the youngster grew up in, but also take into account the social pressures that instrumentalise traits in the name of productivity. I am not using the word 'social' in a sense that would diminish responsibility, however; what emerges from the process of social construction is quite the contrary. Whatever the wiring in the dumb part of the brain, however much hormone is swilling about, an erection (for example!) will be well or badly managed depending on the identity of the sufferer – and the identity has been socially constructed. Hopefully it is now clear why social construction of the identity is so important, not just for managing erections. The social identity *is* the responsible human being, but of course how behaviour is to be judged is a different matter.

So the entire identity, not just the gender, is socially constructed. Social construction has the advantage, or at least what I assume to be the biological advantage, that it is not set in genetic concrete and therefore change on the time scale of cultural change is possible. That relatively radical changes can occur from generation to generation is easy enough to understand, but changes are not so easy for the formed adult individual, even one convinced of the necessity. The mind is in control (and it is in control because it is the top information handler in the chain of information handling, not because it possesses 'will'; forget all that nonsense), but it cannot manage information and values that it does not have access to. How much of the identity is tucked away out of mental sight is difficult to assess and will vary from individual to individual; but what is no longer identified in language is not part of the mind, and routines in this category are acted out unaware. Such behaviour might be misinterpreted as the expression of genetic

traits, an understandable error if no better explanation is available. To put what is inaccessible or ignored by the mind into perspective though, it is perhaps worth pointing out that the capacity of the mind to manage current affairs would be overwhelmed if most of what we do was not driven by habitual 'attitudes'. Stick-in-the-muds will take comfort from that, I guess.

Human beings did not invent social construction; they found it. It is an essential part of the highly successful biological niche that they fell into. Seeing social construction in this evolutionary context should help to counter any ideas about it being a flower-power fantasy. Nobody in their right mind could deny that the description of the evolutionary history of life is the right one and that the mechanism is genetic transmission of information enabling successful survival and reproduction. The evolutionary description has been accepted even though it is not always possible to trace the detailed steps that led from one species to another – just as it is not (yet) possible to trace the steps that lead to a gender identity. The way to look at social construction, in respect to both cultural change and the development of the individual, is to see it as a creative evolutionary mechanism. It represents a step change in the way a living organism (us) handles information: *acquired* information and values are transmitted, not by the genes, but by language. Identity construction has to be considered a very real creative process, rooted in our biology.

How creative can we be? We live in societies that range in character from repressive regimes to liberal nations but not even the best-intentioned state can afford to have for primary objective the personal development and well-being of its citizens. States are struggling to survive in a wicked world and their priority is to develop and make use of the capacities of their citizens - another way of saying that statecraft instrumentalises its population, including its leaders! Our identities – the real people, if you like - are adaptations to the social environment that characterises the state: social class, competition, elitism, hierarchies, fossilised institutions and nationalism. It is not surprising that the resulting identities - all of which are 'like that's', don't forget - include rigid stereotypes, winners and losers... It's for when, the Enlightenment? Rhetorical question. Experience shows that no individual, indeed no ideology, has the capacity to design anything other than a drab version of Utopia. On the other hand, we can surely count on the social creativity that is so well illustrated by the rainbow of gender identities to produce the critics that give regimes a hard time and bags of good advice to the rest.

Just a note for anyone interested in the contribution of two French thinkers to the evolutionary aspects of this debate: I emphasised that social construction is based on the transmission of acquired information that has survival value – survival in society. Transmission of acquired characteristics was an essential ingredient in the thinking of Lamarck, but it turned out not to be the way things happen for the evolution of species. On the other hand, it *is* the mechanism of formation of the mind and culture, which is of course where his intuition came from. I have also stressed the creative aspect of social

construction. Evolution of species is not a creative process, it is reactive not proactive: the environment is constantly changing, and life flows into the niches thereby 'created'. Bergson was an intuitive philosopher keen on the idea that evolution *was* creative but without being able to put his finger on how. You can see that in one special case it is: we are part of the evolutionary story, and we can be proactive. Bergson's intuition, like Lamarck's, was of its time and lacked a solid context, but given their perspicacity, I conclude that it is important always to keep an open mind.